

Mass Spectral Analysis of some Substituted 4-Piperidinones

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Manuscript received 14 May 1993, revised 4 November 1993, accepted 14 December 1993

Although reports on the mass spectral behaviour of a few substituted 4-thianones and substituted 4-selenanones have already appeared^{1,2}, no systematic investigation of the mass spectral behaviour of substituted 4-piperidinones has so far been published with the exception of that for 1-methyl-4-piperidinone³. We report here the mass spectral analysis of some 2,6-diary-4-piperidinones (1-5).

that in compounds 1 and 2 the ring is flattened about the C(2)-C(3) bond, thereby reducing the dihedral angle and hence the coupling constant. The flattening is probably necessitated to reduce the C(2)-aryl and C(3)-alkyl gauche interaction. Not unexpectedly, in compounds 3-5 the benzylic protons couple with the adjacent methine protons with a coupling constant about 10.5 Hz, indicating a uniform ring flattening.

1-3

- 1; Ar = Ph, R₁ = H, R₂ = Et, R₃ = H
2, Ar = *p*-MeOC₆H₄, R₁ = H, R₂ = Me, R₃ = H
3, Ar = *p*-MeOC₆H₄, R₁ = Me, R₂ = Me, R₃ = Me
4, Ar = *p*-MeC₆H₄, R₁ = Me, R₂ = Me, R₃ = Me
5; Ar = *p*-ClC₆H₄, R₁ = H, R₂ = Me, R₃ = Me

The ¹H nmr spectra of these compounds confirm their existence in the chair conformation⁴. In compounds 1 and 2 benzylic protons couple with the adjacent methine protons (giving a doublet) with a coupling constant of about 10 Hz and with the adjacent methylene protons (giving doublets of doublets) with coupling constants around 11.5 and 3 Hz. The large coupling constants (10 and 11.5 Hz) are typical of vicinal diaxial coupling and the much smaller one (3 Hz) is typical of axial-equatorial coupling⁵. The fact that *J*_{2a,3a} is smaller (by more than 10%) than *J*_{5a,6a} suggests

The fragmentation pathways followed by these compounds in the mass spectral analysis may be understood by considering the corresponding behaviour of piperidinone (5), chosen as a representative example. The occurrence of chlorine in nature in two isotopic forms, ³⁵Cl and ³⁷Cl, with abundances respectively of 75 and 25%, enabled us to identify the chlorine containing fragments unambiguously. It appears that the molecular ion of 5 undergoes fragmentation by two major pathways as shown in the Scheme 1. In one, the positive charge is located on nitrogen and in the other, it is located on the carbonyl oxygen.

The base peak probably results from the loss of a neutral 4-membered ring system from the parent ion. In the case of 3-alkylpiperidinones (1 and 2), where the loss of a neutral 4-membered ring will lead to two different fragment ions (due to lack of symmetry in the piperidinone), the predominant cleavage involves the loss of the 3-alkyl group along with the 4-membered ring system. Once again, due to lack of symmetry

Scheme 1

in compounds 1 and 2, fragmentation involving cleavage of C(3)-C(4) bond and that involving cleavage of C(4)-C(5) bond are expected to give rise to two different sets of fragment ions, and all of them have been observed.

Experimental

The piperidinones (1-5) were synthesised following literature procedures^{6,7}. The ¹H nmr spectra were recorded at 400 MHz on a Varian XL-400 spectrometer and the electron impact mass spectra on a VG TS-250 spectrometer. The m/z values and relative intensities (within parentheses) of the various peaks observed in the mass spectra of compounds 1-4 are as follows : 1 m/z 279 (M^+ ; 29%), 195 (11), 194 (39), 174 (20), 160 (2), 159 (3), 147 (10), 146 (8), 132 (19), 131 (89), 119 (2), 105 (47) and 104 (100); 2 m/z 325 (M^+ ; 18%), 255 (5) 254 (24), 190 (7), 176 (2), 175 (3), 163 (3), 162 (10), 161 (24), 149 (4), 148 (10), 135 (26) and 134 (100); 3 m/z 353 (M^+ ; 9%) 269 (1), 254 (4), 190 (9), 177 (2), 176 (3), 175 (3), 149 (14) and 148 (100); 4 m/z 321 (M^+ ; 18%), 237 (1), 222 (3), 188 (4), 161 (4), 160 (4), 159 (10), 133 (20) and 132 (100). The data for the ketone (5) are given in the Schemel.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Principal and the Secretary of C. B. M. College, Coimbatore, for facilities for the synthetic part of this work. One of the authors (K.D.B.) thanks the National Science Foundation for a grant for partial funds to upgrade the XL-300 NMR unit and also thanks the National Science Foundation for a grant for partial funds for the mass spectrometer.

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